

Evaluation of cytoplasmic male sterile and maintainer lines in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated 18 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) A lines (Table 1) and their corresponding maintainers (B lines) in

1993 wet season (WS) at CLRRI. The A lines were planted in two rows and the B lines in four rows, with 25 plants per row. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 2-cm spacing. We evaluated A lines for pollen and spikelet sterility, panicle exertion, and flag leaf length and width. Panicle length, grains/panicle, and grain shape were recorded for B lines. Days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicles/plant and disease reaction were recorded for both A and B lines. To determine

pollen sterility, we collected five florets from five plants before flowering; pollen grains were stained with KI. Spikelet sterility was recorded for five panicles (bagged before emergence) from five plants. Other traits were recorded for five randomly selected plants.

CMS and maintainer lines were evaluated for field reaction to ragged stunt virus and agronomic characteristics (Table 2).

IR62829 A had spikelet fertility of 2% and IR58025 A of 5% in this experiment (Table 1), although in previous seasons at CLRRI, they showed complete pollen and spikelet sterility.

CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A are being used to develop F₁ hybrids for multilocation yield testing in Vietnam. Based on these results, however, CMS and maintainer lines of IR58025, IR62829, and IR64608 must be purified using the pair crossing method. CMS lines IR66707 A, Pragathi A, Madhuri A, PMS8 A, and PMS10 A have good agronomic traits and are suitable for use in the Cuu Long Delta. ■

Table 1. Characteristics of CMS lines in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam. 1993 WS.

CMS line	CMS source	Origin	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Panicle exertion (scale)	Flag leaf (cm)	
						Length	Width
IR58025 A	WA ^a	IRRI	95	95	7	30.7	1.5
IR62829 A	WA	IRRI	95	98	5	28.5	1.0
IR64608 A	WA	IRRI	97	99	7	31.0	1.7
IR67684 A	WA	IRRI	100	100	7	19.0	1.3
IR64607 A	WA	IRRI	98	100	7	32.0	1.3
IR66707 A	<i>O. perennis</i>	IRRI	100	100	3	31.0	1.4
PMS1 A	WA	India	100	100	7	35.5	1.9
PMS8 A	WA	India	100	100	7	41.5	1.7
PMS10 A	WA	India	100	100	7	46.0	1.8
Madhuri A	MS 577	India	95	100	7	32.0	1.6
Pragathi A	MS 577	India	97	100	7	39.5	1.7
Pushpa A	MS 577	India	95	100	7	35.0	1.7
Krishna A	WA	India	93	100	7	21.5	1.7
Krishna A	Kalinga I	India	100	100	7	29.7	1.6
CNTPR10 A	WA	Thailand	100	100	7	29.5	1.8
RD25 A	WA	Thailand	100	100	1	37.5	1.5
RD21 A	WA	Thailand	100	100	1	37.0	1.8
V20 A	WA	China	100	100	7	25.0	1.6

^aWA = wild abortive.

Table 2. Agronomic traits and disease reaction of CMS (A) and maintainer (B) lines. Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam. 1993 WS.

Line	Days to 50% flowering		Plant height (cm)		Panicles/plant (no.)		Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Grain shape ^a	Disease ^b reaction ^c
	A	B	A	B	A	B				
IR58025	81	84	68	85	11.2	6.0	21.0	72.0	LS	S
IR62829	72	72	68	77	16.6	8.2	15.8	49.0	LS	R
IR64608	73	73	69	80	11.0	6.0	17.0	82.0	M	S
IR67684	78	78	69	80	16.0	7.8	21.0	96.0	LS	S
IR64607	84	84	71	91	9.0	7.0	17.8	103.0	LS	MR
IR66707	81	81	71	91	12.5	6.8	17.8	99.6	LS	R
PMS1	87	83	73	85	12.0	7.6	19.6	95.0	LS	S
PMS8	83	79	66	84	17.0	11.0	27.0	113.0	LS	S
PMS10	83	83	65	86	13.0	5.0	23.6	126.0	LS	S
Madhuri	74	74	54	92	16.5	10.2	20.3	72.0	M	R
Pragathi	63	63	54	69	10.0	5.8	26.1	166.0	M	R
Pushpa	74	74	90	95	10.0	7.8	16.8	64.0	M	R
Krishna (WA)	67	67	57	76	13.0	9.8	16.6	48.0	M	S
Krishna (Kalinga)	63	63	54	69	13.0	9.2	19.3	36.6	M	S
CNTPR10	88	88	95	117	6.0	6.0	27.3	120.0	L	R
RD25	68	66	78	85	11.0	9.0	17.3	38.0	L	R
RD21	90	88	113	117	6.6	7.8	22.3	130.0	L	R
V20	62	62	61	73	15.5	8.6	19.0	72.0	M	S

^aLS = long slender, L = long, M = medium. ^bRagged stunt virus. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

A specific esterase band found in Annon-1S

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Isozymes have a noteworthy impact on regulating plant growth and development. To determine the specific proteins of isozymes in thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) rice, we performed vertical polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis at different plant growth stages.

Annon-1S is a natural mutant from indica line Annon-1. Its male sterility by environmental temperature is conditioned. Under high temperatures (daily mean > 26 °C), it has a stable sterile stage. The higher the temperature, the earlier the pollen development stage, which results in sterility. When temperature falls below the threshold, partial or normal fertility occurs. Studies indicate that a pair of recessive nuclear genes controls sterility and that segregating generations have goodness of fit to the Mendelian rules with respect to the trait.

Effect of maltose and hormones on callus formation and plant regeneration in isolated microspore culture of japonica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Microspore culture provides an ideal system for genetic manipulation in plants. Its efficiency in rice, however, is quite poor. We studied the effects of maltose, 2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D), and naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) on callus formation and plant regeneration from microspore culture of rice.

Three japonica cultivars and five liquid media were used (see table). The anthers with microspores at the middle to late uninucleate stage were pretreated at $6^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 17 d, then precultured onto liquid medium for another 5 d at $27^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. After that, the microspores were isolated from the anther with a glass rod

and washed with the same medium. The extract was filtered through a nylon sieve (100 μm pore size) and the filtrate was precipitated for 20 min, then centrifuged at $100 \times g$ for 2 min. The 2 ml of medium containing microspores in the bottom of the tube was cultured in petri dishes at a density of about 4.0×10^4 pollen grains/ml and kept in the dark at $27^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for callusing. Number of calli was recorded after 35 d.

Calli as large as 1.0-1.5 mm in diameter were transferred to medium of the same composition, solidified with 0.6% (w/v) agar. When calli became about 2 mm long, they were transferred to plant regeneration medium.

Only a few microspores in M1 and M2 media, which contained sucrose, divided without any callus formation. A high frequency of callus induction occurred, however, when microspores were cultured on media with maltose as the carbon source (Fig. 1a, b). All three genotypes responded well to the M3 medium, producing many calli. The frequency of callus formation could be raised by increasing the concentration of 2,4-D from

1. Strong expression of s band at sterile stage of TGMS and PGMS lines. 1-3: N422S; 6-8 Annong-1S; 4-5: Bodat Mayang (check).

2. S-band at four-leaf-old seedling stage of Annong-1S. 1-3: Annong-1S; 4-6: Annong-1 (check).

We used an improved method to conduct an esterase isozyme assay based on our prior work, adopting the discontinuous separating system. The staining method of M. Nakagahra was used.

Seven isozyme bands can be separated under our system of electrophoresis. We detected *Est-1* and *Est-2* isozyme bands at both the germinated seed stage and at all other growth stages and *Est-3* band at only the mature-leaf stage. A specific esterase band (s band) was discovered in Annong-1S and N422S, a photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) line derived from Nongken 58S (Fig. 1). Annong 1 and 210 other normal rice varieties did not have this s band. Its stable expression in mature leaves and unstable expression in young leaf blades are detectable in some PGMS and TGMS lines derived from Nongken 58S and Annong-1S (Fig. 2). We are conducting further studies on linkage analysis in segregating generations and its genetics. ■

a) Microspores started to divide after 5 d of culture (X60). b) Microcalli derived from microspore after 7-10 d of culture (X50). c) Green plantlet.

Effect of maltose and hormones on callus formation and plant regeneration of isolated rice microspore culture.

Genotype	Callus induction medium ^a	Calli/anther (no.) ^b	Calli for regeneration (no.)	Plant regeneration ^c			
				Green		Albino	
				no.	%	no.	%
02428	M1	0	-	-	-	-	-
Xiushu 117	M1	0	-	-	-	-	-
Taipei 309	M1	0	-	-	-	-	-
02428	M2	0	-	-	-	-	-
Xiushu 117	M2	0	-	-	-	-	-
Taipei 309	M2	0	-	-	-	-	-
02428	M3	1.48	178	-	-	50	28.6
Xiushu 117	M3	1.38	145	1	0.7	-	-
Taipei 309	M3	1.24	269	26	9.7	63	23.4
Taipei 309	M4	1.66	155	9	5.8	35	22.6
Taipei 309	M5	0.46	148	18	12.2	69	46.6

^aM1 = MS salts + 100 mg/liter myoinositol + 1.0 mg/liter thiamine-HCl + 500 mg/liter glutamine + 0.5 mg/liter 2,4-D + 30 g/liter sucrose, pH 5.8; M2 = M1 + 30 g/liter sucrose; M3 = 60 g/liter maltose in place of 60 g/liter sucrose in M2; M4 = M3 + 0.5 mg/liter 2,4-D; M5 = M4 + 1.0 mg/liter NAA. ^bValues are means of three replications. ^cMS agar medium supplemented with 1 mg/liter vitamin B₁, 0.5 mg/liter vitamin B₆, 2 mg/liter glycine, 0.5 mg/liter nicotinic acid, 100 mg/liter myoinositol, 2 mg/liter kinetin, and 0.5 mg/liter indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), pH 5.8.